

REQUIREMENTS FOR THE IMAGE OF A MODERN TEACHER

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8417194>

Abstract. *In this article, in the organization of the educational process in general secondary schools and higher education, and in the education of students, in connection with the formation of teachers as modern specialists in accordance with the requirements of the time, as well as the issues of their image as pedagogues explained.*

Keywords: *image of teacher, modern pedagogue, pedagogical skills, perseverance, psychologist, pedagogue.*

Teaching is a profession that has been respected since the beginning of the history of human society, and at the same time, it has always been respected by the society and the public.

"... A teacher - says Al Farabi - needs to have intelligence, beautiful speech, and be able to fully and clearly express the thoughts he wants to convey to the students." He continued his opinion: "The task of a teacher and leader is similar to the task of a wise head of state, so a teacher should remember everything he heard and saw, have intelligence, beautiful speech, and he should know how to fully and clearly express his thoughts to the teachers. At the same time, he should value his honor and be fair. Only then will he have a high level of humanity and reach the peak of happiness," he says.

A modern school teacher performs a number of tasks. The teacher is the organizer of the learning process in the classroom. The teacher is one of the sources of knowledge for the students in providing the necessary advice during the lesson, in extra lessons and at the same time in extracurricular situations. Many teachers are the organizers of the educational process, acting as the head of the class.

A modern teacher cannot be a social psychologist. Therefore, it is necessary to be able to establish mutual relations between students, to know how to use social-psychological mechanisms in the children's group.

It is known that pedagogical activity is one of the most complex areas of human labor. The most important of the requirements set by the society is focused on the teacher's personality and qualities related to his profession.

The demands placed on the teacher by the society, various social expectations, the individuality of the pedagogue, and his subjective readiness to respond to these demands indicate the level of readiness of a particular teacher for pedagogical activity.

The qualities of a modern school teacher, who is carrying out an important state task - the national personnel training program, his creative activity grows and develops mainly in practical work, in the process of acquiring pedagogical experiences. At the same time, it is necessary for the teacher to constantly improve his qualifications and cultivate his personal qualities that help ensure the success of his work at a high level.

The place and role of the teacher for the society is incomparable. Their level leads the society either to the bottom or to the top. It should be understood that a teacher is a hugely

responsible, free-thinking and growing knowledge holder. Modernity is its mandatory quality, as much as it demands its knowledge. That is, if knowledge is not adapted to this time, its value and value will decrease. Therefore, a broad worldview, free thinking and modernity are mandatory professional requirements of a teacher.

The basis of development in any field is the quality and efficiency of the educational process in that field. Because development is influenced by specialist personnel who have acquired knowledge, skills, and competencies in the relevant fields ("hard skills") through the process of certain educational stages. When the educational process is properly organized and the necessary conditions for education are created, it is possible to achieve the goal of education, that is, to train quality personnel. The conditions that positively affect the quality of the educational process, which must be created, include the material and technical base in accordance with the requirements of the time, the encouragement and material support of pedagogues-employees, the protection of their rights and interests, and the improvement of their qualifications. , creation of a positive socio-psychological climate for pedagogues-employees, favorable for creative, development and development work, where constructive relations prevail. The achievement of independence of Uzbekistan, the construction of a new society based on the principles set by our president, fundamental reforms in the education system, major changes in people's minds, turning the slogan "Uzbekistan's future great state" into a reality is a professor in the higher education system in many ways. -depends on the potential of teachers, personal qualities and their position in society. The image of a pedagogue in higher education determines the maintenance of the above requirements. The higher their image, the more intellectuals among young people devote themselves to this field, turn it into a professional activity, and on the contrary, if the image of a pedagogue is not at a sufficient level, intellectual young people try to avoid this profession.

Therefore, the image of the pedagogue in the higher education system can be considered as one of the important factors determining the economic and social development of the country. Today, for some reasons, there is a need to raise the image of a modern pedagogue to a sufficient level, because it is not at the level of demand. In our opinion, today we can see a lot of changes in the image of intellectuals, including pedagogues in the higher education system, which can be observed inevitably in the transition period of all developed countries. Factors causing them, causes, duration of changes, negative and positive, social and territorial characteristics determine the urgency of the problem chosen by the need for special scientific research. It is necessary to research the socio-psychological factors of the formation of the image of a modern pedagogue operating in society today, to psychologically analyze the role of social psychological mechanisms and factors in the formation of the spiritual image of a modern pedagogue.

When talking about the essence of the concept of image, it should be noted that the image is a formed image aimed at a goal, and is a generalized form of emotional and psychological impact on the public. The image of a teacher is an emotional, colorful and strong image of a teacher, and it affects the behavior of the students in the imagination of the people around them. The image of a pedagogue is formed on the basis of expenses aimed at the goal of successful activity. The topic of the teacher's image is a hot topic of discussion in scientific literature today. But in all views, a positive image is considered the main factor of successful pedagogical activity. An image is an image, a person is considered a system of external characteristics, which determines the uniqueness of a person. Always reflects his individuality in his communication with other people.

Image elements form an integral part of a person's character and individuality and shape the attitude of people around him.

Adding the word "Image" to the vocabulary of pedagogical activity is not an imitation of fashion. A pedagogue rises to the leadership level with his personal growth and illuminates his efficiency and qualities in his professional work. Usually, the image is manifested in the form of a formed image, and the influence of positive qualities and characteristics on the surrounding people is understood. The image consists of a set of opinions expressed about a person based on relationships. M. Ochilov, who studied the teacher's pedagogical skills in the direction of "Ethical formation of the teacher", emphasizes that ethics is an important source of acquiring pedagogical skills, and describes the moral norms of the profession as follows: "Engage in a certain field of activity there are also moral norms and requirements that apply to people with disabilities. Such ethics are called profession (professional) ethics.

There is a certain relationship between the prevailing morality and professional ethics in every society. This is the relationship between generality and particularity. He says that professional ethics embodies, clarifies and develops the rules and shortcomings of universal moral theory. "A teacher - says Al Farabi - needs to have intelligence, a beautiful speech, and be able to fully and clearly express the thoughts he wants to convey to students." He continued his opinion and said, "The task of a teacher and a leader is similar to the task of a wise head of state, therefore, the teacher should remember everything he heard and saw, have intelligence, and beautiful speech to the students. he should know how to express his thoughts fully and clearly. At the same time, he should value his dignity and be fair. Only then will he have a high level of humanity and reach the peak of happiness." According to the encyclopedist Abu Ali ibn Sina, "A teacher should be tenacious, honest, honest and well-versed in the methods and morals of child education. The teacher should be able to study the entire inner and outer world of the student and get into the layers of his mind." Nasiruddin Tusi says in his work "On Educating Teachers": "A teacher knows how to prove when conducting discussions, believes in the correctness of his thoughts, and his speech is absolutely clean, and his sentences are logically expressed should be. A teacher's speech can never be abusive, rude or harsh. Creating the image of a modern pedagogue increases the effectiveness of education in the continuous education system, leads to the modernization of pedagogical activities, and creates the basis for the establishment of a prosperous society, which is the main idea of our national ideology. In connection with the transition to new standards, special attention is paid to the professional skills of a person, his achievement of high positions, development of his personal culture, and innovative creative research. In our opinion, it is important to include the process of modeling personal identity and emotions in the development of the pedagogue's identity and knowledge, improving the logicity, the concept of unifying the identity, visualizing, finding new, professional and original solutions possible.

In a day when the development and renewal of the educational system is of great importance in our lives, the professional skills and image of pedagogues are becoming increasingly important. To a large extent, the successful activity of a pedagogue depends on his ability to influence others positively and to what extent. It is required that the inner and outer world of the pedagogue should be in harmony (harmony), and that his thoughts and actions should be reflected in the work he is doing.

For the teacher, the image is much more important than for representatives of other fields, it leads to the emergence of imagination in students, the emergence of positive assumptions and,

in turn, the formation of their image. The main qualities of a teacher's personality should be his communicativeness, reflexivity, self-control, and empathy. To form an image, it is necessary to study the motive, in which psychologists emphasize that there is a difference between an image that is focused on feelings (extrinsic motivation) and a full feeling of self (internal motivation). Depending on the motivation, the appropriate tactics of image formation are chosen: self-awareness, self-masking, self-presentation as a form of self-image. Psychological characteristics of a person can be taken as a basis for creating an image of a subject that corresponds to one's consciousness and the quality of the subject. Psychology studies the image of the complex - appearance, verbal and non-verbal aspects expressed by the interrelated components of the image. The image of psychologists is not limited to the development of some informative formula necessary to achieve certain goals. In this case, the process of psychological support of a person is reasonable, especially this issue is relevant in the case of coaching. From the point of view of psychology, the image is the only tool for evaluating a person. The science of psychology evaluates the image as a factor that transforms its appearance into a socio-psychological influence, which changes the methods of administrative management.

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